
LATEX LLM ONCOLOGY TABLE PROMPTING GUIDE

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LaTeX Table Prompting Guide For Better & Faster Oncology Publications

Prior Table Templates

- Goals: b) Transfer data from prior markdown tables, c) but disregard a prior LaTeX template's information
- Prompt: "Based on the attached LaTeX table template, convert each of the following markdown tables into new LaTeX tables."
- Prompt: "Do not use the information from the template, simply use the template as a formatting guide to follow."
- LaTeX: Incorporate from author's prior .tex file OR open-source LaTeX code: arXiv, online literature
- LaTeX: `\begin{tabular}`, `\end{tabular}` tabular environment converted from markdown; other input files work

Structural Table Editing 1

- Goals: Add a caption and label to the new LLM-generated LaTeX tables
- Prompt: "Provide an appropriate concise caption (no longer than 2 lines) and label for each new table."
- LaTeX: `\caption{}`, `\label{}` structural elements auto-completed in new table generations

Structural Table Editing 2

- Goals: Automate LaTeX vertical and horizontal table spacing options
- Prompt: "Include `arraystretch` and `tablecolsep` in every table."
- LaTeX: `\arraystretch{}`, `\tablecolsep{}`: vertical spacing between rows, horizontal spacing between columns

Structural Table Editing 3

- Goals: Save significant time formatting columns by having LLM set column widths that can be easily adjusted
- Prompt: "Do not use the exact number of rows and columns from the template, instead use the appropriate number of rows and columns, while specifying custom column widths accordingly for each table."
- LaTeX: Example: `{p{1.7cm} p{2.5cm} p{0.8cm} p{0.8cm}}` Authors: request custom column widths for every table

Structural Table Editing 4

- Goals: Avoid unprofessional tables with excessive white spacing between words
- Prompt: "Make sure all `\raggedright` text looks like it is truly left justified, with no large spaces between words using techniques such as `\raggedright\arraybackslash`."
- LaTeX: `>\raggedright\arraybackslash` is left-aligned to avoid excessive inter-word spacing

Structural Table Editing 5

- Goals: Force source markdown files to fully populate captions and labels appropriately
- Prompt: "Any additional relevant information from the markdown files can be used in titles and captions."
- LaTeX: `\caption{}`, `\label{}` structural elements in new LaTeX tables are correctly populated from source data

Table Layout Constraints

- Goals: Encourage each generated table to stay in a certain position
- Prompt: "Every table must use `minipage` as shown in the template."
- LaTeX: `\begin{minipage}\textwidth, \end{minipage}` constrains table vertically positioning to a specific page

Original Full Prompt: Based on the attached LaTeX table template, convert each of the following markdown tables into new LaTeX tables. Do not use the information from the template, simply use the template as a formatting guide to follow. Provide an appropriate concise caption (no longer than 2 lines) and label for each new table. Include `arraystretch` and `tablecolsep` in every table. Each table must not be any longer than one page; do not use longtable for any of the tables. Make sure all `\raggedright` text looks like it is truly left justified, with no large spaces between words using techniques such as `\raggedright\arraybackslash`. Any additional relevant information from the markdown files can be used in titles and captions. Every table must use `minipage` as shown in the template. [doi:10.5281/zenodo.18029100, Section 5.3]